

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NAMBORO KETTE****FIRST NAME: Issa Omer****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the fundamental structure of academic essay writing?

- Introduction, body and conclusion.**¹
- Organization of ideas, research of the subject, writing.
- Bibliography, reference, table of contents.
- Citation of sources, good usage of grammar, good usage of punctuation.

2. Which of these sentences is true :

- Use punctuation to separate ideas.
- Use punctuation to explain a sentence.
- Uses punctuation to indicate that a letter is omitted.

¹Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

- Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence.²

3. How to reference a text by the notes style?

- In notes style, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote or otherwise refer to that source.³

- By giving the name of the author.
- By quoting the author's sentence.
- By avoiding plagiarism.

4. How to reference a text by the author-date style?

- By giving the name of the author.
- In author-date style, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to that source.⁴
- By avoiding plagiarism.
- By indicating the year of publication and the page number.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 16.

³Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 147.

⁴ Turabian, 228.

5. What is the research?
- Answer a question.
 - Deal with a research topic.
 - Build a research project.
 - A specific way to mean a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher, but also others want to solve.⁵**
6. How can you write a reference list?
- By writing in alphabetical order.
 - By writing by bibliographic entries.
 - By writing Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.⁶**
 - By writing Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.
7. What are the components of a research dissertation?
- Introduction, body, conclusion.
 - Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, dissertation manuscript.⁷**

⁵ Turabian, 19.

⁶ Turabian, 229.

⁷ James P. Sampson, Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee: College of Education and Florida State University, 2017), 2-5.

- Bibliography, reference, citation.
 - Editor's name, biography, date of birth.
8. What are the initial parts of a research dissertation?
- Title, supervisory committee page, dedication, acknowledgements, table of content, list of tables, list of figures, bibliography, abstract.**⁸
 - Introduction, body, conclusion.
 - Concept paper, dissertation.
 - Dissertation prospectus, dissertation manuscript.
9. What do you know about the European Union?
- Organization of all the countries of Europe.
 - Organization comprising only the combined territories of its Member States (certain European countries).**⁹
 - Organization of the European Economic Community.
 - Organization of the European Commission.
10. The institutions of the European Union are:
- The Commission, the Council, the European Council, the European Parliament, the European Court of Justice, the Court of Auditors of the**

⁸Sampson, Jr, 24-26.

⁹ European Union, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition: January 2016 (Bruxelles: European Commission, 2021), 71.

European Union, the Economic and Social Committee of the European Union, the Committee of the Regions.¹⁰

- The Economic Community of Coal and Steel and the European Bank.
- The International Court of Justice and the International Criminal Court.
- The Economic and Social Council and the Security Council.

¹⁰ European Union, 84-91.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.